

Taking action to prevent and mitigate pollution of groundwater bodies

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Deliverable 6.2

Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDEC)

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Partners short names

Number	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country
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4	BEN	WETSUS	STICHTING WETSUS, EUROPEAN CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE FOR SUSTAINABLE WATER TECHNOLOGY	NL
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6	BEN	Deltares	STICHTING DELTARES	NL
7	BEN	UNIROMA1	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA	IT
8	BEN	AQUALIA	FCC AQUALIA SA	ES
8.1	AE	HIDROTEC	HIDROTEC TECNOLOGIA DEL AGUA SL	ES
9	BEN	AYTO ALCÁZARES	AYUNTAMIENTO DE LOS ALCAZARES	ES

Abbreviations

PDEC	Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
WP	Work Package
GW	Groundwater
DSS	Decision support system
P1	During the project and 1 year after its end
DoA	Description of Action
P2	The next 5 years
SHG	Stakeholder Group
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

Executive Summary

NINFA Deliverable 6.2, the first version of the "Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication" (PDEC), aims to maximize the impact of the project by outlining the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) activities that will be undertaken by the consortium as part of WP6. The plan includes an analysis of target groups, proposed channels for interacting with stakeholders, communication measures, policy feedback measures, and a follow-up plan to foster the exploitation and uptake of all the NINFA results. CETRI, the WP6 leader, will coordinate all partners' active participation in DEC actions.

All partners will conduct awareness campaigns in their respective countries and networks, contribute news and updates to the web portal and newsletter, and keep the project's social media accounts active. They will also translate required material into local languages to amplify the impact of NINFA. The development of all communication tools is CETRI's responsibility. In Deliverable 6.1 submitted in month 3, a range of communication tools were displayed including the website, promotional material and social media channels. More tools will be presented in this deliverable to further promote the project and its objectives.

This document outlines the dissemination and communication strategy of the NINFA consortium and serves as a reference for partners to implement their individual and joint DEC activities.

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1 Introduction

NINFA aims to prevent groundwater (GW) contamination through a series of innovative and cost-effective monitoring, modelling and treatment solutions and by using a novel decision support system (DSS) for sustainable GW management.

The PDEC deliverable plays a crucial role in achieving NINFA's overall objective of maximizing the impact of its outcomes in the EU, associated countries, and worldwide. The main aim of the PDEC is to develop a common strategy for the consortium that effectively communicates and disseminates project results to relevant stakeholders, ultimately promoting and utilizing these results.

The PDEC has been developed by CETRI with the active involvement of all partners and it has been set up by M6 of the project as a valuable resource that partners can use as a reference point/guidance for implementing their various DEC activities. The plan will be updated throughout the project's lifetime according to the needs and requirements that may arise. Additionally, this plan will be used as the main input for the final PDEC in month 42 as described in the DoA.

2 Objectives of Deliverable

The PDE's objective is to outline a dynamic strategy for partners to plan and execute communication and dissemination activities, with specific monitoring tools and materials provided by CETRI. The project community will continuously support dissemination efforts to facilitate exploitation of all results. A high project visibility and active stakeholder interaction are essential to build project awareness, maximize exploitation potential, and promote accountability that justifies the use of public funds to support this Research & Innovation Action project.

Early dissemination planning is essential to increase impact and collaboration opportunities and ensure project outputs are fully exploited. This approach also promotes the sharing of knowledge with interested organizations, the reuse of excellent elements, informing decision-makers, and highlighting the project's societal benefits.

3 Dissemination & Communication Strategy

Dissemination and communication activities will be complementary and synergistic, targeting a wide range of stakeholders. Partners will disseminate the project results to audiences that are expected to use the results in their own work, including scientific community in water treatment, groundwater monitoring/management/protection, farmers, water utilities, policymakers, authorities. The whole consortium will also communicate the project and its results to multiple audiences beyond the project's own community including citizens, investors and media, informing and reaching out to society, highlighting the importance of preventing GW contamination and protecting its quality.

4 Target Audience and Key Messages

When creating a plan for communication and dissemination, it's essential to know the target audience. Since the NINFA goals and outcomes may interest a diverse range of audiences, identifying the target audience is critical. Once the audience is determined, the best communication methods and channels can be selected. Additionally, evaluating the effectiveness of the PDEC becomes more manageable by monitoring how the message is received by the target audience. This approach enables necessary changes to the PDEC to ensure that it effectively reaches and engages with the audience. By continuously evaluating the communication strategy, a more effective and targeted plan can be developed to meet the audience's needs.

The next important step is to create messages that are specifically tailored to the identified target group. To achieve effective communication, messages must be relevant, aligned with project objectives, and engaging to the groups of interest.

Table 1 contains key messages that emphasize the advantages of NINFA and their relevance to specific target groups. The table also outlines the tools and channels necessary for effectively communicating these messages to the intended audience. These messages will be refined as the project progresses to better suit the target group, dissemination actions (such as publications, articles, and events), and communication tools (including leaflets, presentations, and social media posts). The wording and tone of these messages will be adjusted accordingly to optimize their impact.

Table 1 NINFA Target Groups

Target groups	How to reach them	Key message
Water Industry (WI): Public and private water utilities, water treatment companies, water associations, water managers responsible for monitoring and inspecting GW pollution, water agencies, consulting, ICT / IOT companies.	B2B meetings, invitation at project events and workshops, online and face to face meetings, social media. P1>100, P2>400	Huge profits for investing in a new generation of water treatment and GW monitoring/management solutions. Access a new network of water stakeholders in Europe.
Policymakers (PM): Authorities and experts on regulatory and policy issues related to GW contamination, EC agencies (e.g., ECHA, EEA), environmental and health-related NGOs, working/advisory groups on water pollution.	Invitation at project events and workshops, online and face to face meetings, social media. P1>70, P2>500	NINFA will incorporate innovations in prevention/mitigation of GW contamination that will implement/recommend existing/new regulations.
Governance bodies (G): Local and regional authorities developing and implementing GW management plans, ministries of environment / agriculture.	F2F meetings, invitation at project events and workshops. P1>80, P2>1k	NINFA will prevent GW pollution, protecting public health and creating new tourism opportunities. Growth in water sector and new jobs.
Scientific Community (SC): Leading researchers in the key areas of hydrogeology; pollution prevention; GW monitoring, management and protection; water treatment; nutrients management; agronomy; etc.	Publications, articles, conferences, workshops, research networks, clustering. P1>10k, P2>90k	All data and information created /Collected during the project, not bound to IPR constraints, will be available on open royalty-free basis.
Farming Industry (FI): Farmers, farming associations, cooperatives, Chambers of Agriculture, agribusiness professionals, advisors.	Exhibitions, fairs, workshops, media. P1>400, P2>500	Comply with upcoming stricter regulations, grow healthier products, protect your health, reduce costs (fertilisers, pesticides, water).
Research Projects (RP): Horizon Europe, H2020, PRIMA, LIFE+, other European funding streams on addressing water pollution issues.	Clustering activities, common workshops/dissemination activities. P1>50, P2>150	Let's partner up to maximize our combined impact and reach as many stakeholders as possible.

Investors (I): Funding bodies, private equity firms, venture capital investors, innovation brokers.	B2B meetings, invitation to project events and workshops. P1>60, P2>300	High ROI by investing in the NINFA Platform and Solutions.
Media (M): Websites, portals, popular YouTubers, journalists, internet / social media influencers, local TV stations, newspapers, radio stations.	Targeted articles, videos, Infographics, advertisements. P1>300, P2>1k	Promote our EU funded project that prevents GW pollution protecting public health and environment.
General public (GP): Citizens interested in water quality and environmental issues, CSOs interested in sustainable water management.	Social media, public events, publications videos, website, podcasts. P1>100k, P2>1M	Be part of the Pan-European effort to ensure quality and sustainable water for all!

5 Dissemination Plan

Choosing the most effective dissemination activities to accomplish the NINFA objectives and target the appropriate audience is crucial. The project team brings together a diverse range of expertise from various disciplines with valuable connections to prominent scientific and industrial networks in Europe, enabling direct collaboration with these groups. Table 2 summarizes the primary dissemination tools, identified by the NINFA project team, but it should be noted that this list is dynamic and will be revised continuously as the project progresses.

Table 2 NINFA Dissemination Tools

Dissemination tools	Performance indicators		Means of Verification
	P1	P2	
Publications in high impact journals or international scientific conferences on hydrogeology, GW management and protection, water treatment, etc.	At least 10 peer-reviewed articles submitted	>15 peer-reviewed articles	List of Publications
Official EU Key Tools as the Horizon Results Platform, Horizon Dashboard, CORDIS, and the Innovation Radar, EU magazines as Euronews, Horizon Magazine, Project Stories, research*eu results magazine	Use of all Key Tools. 5 articles published at EU magazines	6 popular articles published at EU magazines	Project Reporting
Articles published in environmental magazines	At least 5 articles	At least 5 articles	Project Reporting
Best practices Handbook (publicly available and free to download) presenting lessons learnt during the project, suggesting best practices in the area and providing policy recommendations	>1000 views / downloads	1,500 new downloads	Website Analytics
Diffusion of project results to associations' members: UNIROMA: International Association of Hydrogeologists, European Federation of Geologists. WETSUS: Water Europe, Water4All partnership, Top sector Water. IMT: DREAM cluster (water cluster), International Water Association, ASTEE. DEL: International Association of Hydrogeologists, NICOLE. LEITAT: Catalan Water Partnership, Water Europe, WAITRO	>100 organisations	>800 organisations	Project Reporting
Research educational activities: MSc and PhD theses related to NINFA research	>2PhD, >3MSc >300 students reached	>5PhD, >10MSc >500 students reached	Project Reporting
Clustering and networking activities with stakeholders, relevant initiatives, and similar projects	3 joint actions, formation of a policy forum	5 joint actions	Project Reporting

5.1 Dissemination actions up to month 6

Since the start of the project on 1 Nov. 2023,

- **LEITAT (P1)**
 - 1) Organized the kick-off meeting of NINFA in Leitat Technological Center, in Barcelona and the 2nd day the whole consortium visited its main Research facilities in Terrassa (half hour trip from Barcelona center).
 - 2) Participated in the Workshop with title “EU funded project Greener Workshop” in Terrassa, Spain, on 24 April 2023
- **LEITAT, UNIROMA1 & CETRI** participated in the kick-off meeting of the ZeroPollution4water cluster, held online on 9 March 2023 (See Annex 2)
- **UNIROMA1 (P7)**
 - 1) Participated in the “Groundwater summit in Rome (UNESCO headquarters) on 6-8 Dec 2022. <https://groundwater-summit.org/>
 - 2) Attended the workshop “First Consultative Water4All SRIA Workshop for Experts” of the WATER4ALL European Partnership. Held in Helsinki, Finland, on February 16-17, 2023.
 - 3) Attended a meeting on Groundwater for Sustainable development goals (SDG) in Sapienza Università di Roma in Rome, on 22 March 2023. (World water day)
- **LOS ALCÁZARES (P9)** together with **AQUALIA (P8)**
 - 1) Organized a press release event at the City Hall of Los Alcázares in Spain to promote NINFA. <https://www.orm.es/noticias-2023/los-alczares-contribuira-con-el-proyecto-ninfa-a-proteger-el-mar-menor/>
- **All partners** contribute in promoting NINFA via posts in personal social media accounts, but mostly in LinkedIn and Twitter.

5.2 Dissemination actions in the future

To promote project participation through NINFA communication channels, CETRI has asked partners to inform both LEITAT and itself about any new events they will be participating in at least one week before the event. Following the event, partners are asked to utilize the NINFA D&C reporting template' (See Annex 2) to monitor progress. The participating partner fills out the document and sends it back to both LEITAT and CETRI. For saving time in the gathering process, it is also available in the NINFA repository (EXT-NINFA Microsoft Teams folder), accessible to all partners.

As the project progresses, partners will plan and schedule activities/events in which they intend to participate and disseminate the project results. Such as: presentations in conferences, organization of events, networking with other projects.

5.2.1 Actions planned

The following activities have been planned by certain partners:

- **WETSUS (P4)** is planning to do the following:
 - 1) Create a movie about the development and installation of the multi-sensory device at Los Alcázares Field (CS2, Spain). (Sept. 2024)

- 2) Prepare a paper on the effects of drought on groundwater quality in the Achterhoek area (Netherlands). The paper will describe as well possible solutions to the problem (2024).
 - 3) A congress session "Managed aquifer recharge for drought resilience" is planned. The Wetsus congress will be held in October 2023.
 - 4) During the Wetsus congress the NINFA M13 Consortium meeting will also be held in order to increase the visibility of the project.
 - 5) The development of the multisensory device and the results that will be obtained during the fieldwork will be published at an international conference (2025).
 - 6) A report will be developed and sent to the water authorities outlining solutions and measures for reducing the drought's impact on groundwater quality at the Achterhoek and Los Alcázares study areas (2025).
- **DELTA RES, WETSUS and UNIROMA1** will attend and make a presentation in the "Amsterdam International Water week" in Amsterdam on 6-9 Nov. 2023.
 - Second online meeting of the ZeroPollution4water cluster is planned for the first week of June 2023 to discuss the strategy and the working group organization.

5.2.2 Clustering activities

Several projects under two different calls but with similar objectives and goals have been identified as sister projects of NINFA and created the ZeroPollution4water cluster under the coordination of "Water Europe".

1. UPWATER - Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081807>
2. MAR2PROTECT -Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082048>
3. SafeCREW - Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081980>
4. ToDriQ – Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082035>
5. H2OforAll -Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081963>
6. intoDBP -Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081728>

The cluster aims at creating further collaboration and synergy between the sister projects, developing co-operation actions with other projects running and future projects – not necessarily funded by the EU R&I FP. Collaborating in a collective effort can lead to a critical mass of knowledge and expertise to effectively participate in the debate on water effective management, from the zero-pollution strategy viewpoint, thus contributing to policy development, R&I's new challenges identification, and exploitation of results to achieve a Water-Smart Society. These actions clearly demonstrate the long-term benefits of the EU funding to research, innovation and policy formation.

6 Communication Plan

The primary aim of the communication plan is to implement a range of activities and tools that will promote the project, its main purpose, and objectives to diverse audiences beyond the project's immediate community. The goal is to raise awareness and engage with society, emphasizing the significance of innovative groundwater management technologies that can minimize the environmental impact on water pollution.

The communication plan encompasses various elements, a number of which were described in detail in the deliverable 6.1 including the project's visual identity, website, leaflet and social media profiles. In the present deliverable, the newly designed roll-up banner is presented, as well as the social media profiles updated analytics. However, to ensure completeness and facilitate accessibility all the promotional materials are displayed together.

All the project materials will be produced in English. In case a partner/s wish to translate the materials into their local language for use in regional activities, the cost will be their responsibility.

6.1 Visual identity

The project's visual identity has been designed by WP6 Leader CETRI and incorporated into project document templates: deliverables, meeting agenda, meeting minutes, and PowerPoint presentation and have been uploaded in the EXT-NINFA Microsoft Teams folder, accessible to all partners.

The NINFA promotional materials that have developed so far are:

- NINFA Logo and colour guide
- NINFA Deliverable template
- NINFA Presentation template
- NINFA Agenda template
- NINFA Minutes template
- NINFA Leaflet
- NINFA roll up banner

6.1.1 Ninfa Logo

This unique logo is the primary representation of the project and expresses its distinct visual character. See Figure 1 below

Figure 1 - NINFA logo

Furthermore, the EU flag and the following disclaimer (Figure 2) will be present in all forms of communication.

Figure 2 - EU Flag & Disclaimer

6.1.2 Ninfa colours

The NINFA colour schemes shown in Figure 3 are the two colours used in the logo and can be utilized throughout the project materials to organize and emphasize various sections of content.

These colours will also influence the colour scheme of all other communication materials (templates, leaflets, rollup banner, social media platforms, articles)

Figure 3 - NINFA LOGO colours

6.1.3 Ninfa Templates

CETRI has created a number of NINFA templates in order to maintain consistency in the layout and appearance of all project uses. The templates that have been developed so far are:

- NINFA Deliverable template
- NINFA agenda.
- NINFA minutes
- NINFA Powerpoint presentation

All the templates feature the project logo, the EU flag and disclaimer, and the NINFA colours and text font. They can be found in the EXT-NINFA Teams folder. In order to utilize the templates as effective communication tools, it is important for all partners to use the correct templates for their intended purposes.

6.2 Website

The NINFA website (www.ninfa-project.eu) has been launched since the beginning of the project by CETRI. The website structure and design are presented below in Table 1.

Table 3 – NINFA website structure

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Home	Project	Outputs	Communication & Dissemination	Newsletter	Sister Projects	News
	Objective	Public Deliverables	Publications			
	Structure		Conferences			
	Partners		Videos			
			Gallery			
			Promotional Material			

As the project develops, the website will undergo frequent updates with continuous contribution from the partners. The latest developments will be shared through newsletters, press releases, research outputs, and deliverables, all available on the project website. These updates aim to generate interest and engage with diverse sectors of society.

The website contains links to the social account platform on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. All public deliverables generated for the project will be accessible to all visitors and easy to download. To track the impact of the website through the number of visitors, google analytics has

been enabled and will be monitored continuously. The NINFA homepage is shown as screenshots in Annex 1.

6.3 NINFA leaflet

CETRI has produced a NINFA leaflet to be distributed at conferences and other relevant events related to groundwater management and protection, across EU countries. The leaflet is threefold and it includes: 1) project logo, title and website, 2) partners logos, 3) project information, 4) social media platforms, 5) the challenge, 6) the solution and 7) who benefits. It is presented below in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - NINFA leaflet

6.4 NINFA roll up banner

CETRI has created a rollup banner for use at conferences, workshops, and other events related to NINFA. The banner features the project's logo, title, contact information, and logos of the consortium and funding sources. The design aims to provide a clear understanding of the project within a brief 10-second glance.

Figure 5 - NINFA rollup banner

Furthermore, as the project continues to advance, more promotional materials will be developed to portray the research done, the new findings and any related news. Such as:

- A poster will soon be developed to be used in workshops or any other event the partners will attend. It can be designed in line with the specific event.
- Videos and podcasts with project information and interviews will be produced.
- Extra promotional material will be needed due to clustering activities with sister projects.
- e-Newsletter will be published every six months summarising all activities related to the project and targeting the research and academic community, water industry and policymakers.

6.5 Social media channels

It is important to develop a social media strategy in order to promote the NINFA project effectively. CETRI has started to create posts (kick-off meeting material, lab setups (milestone 1, meetings) and with the increased contribution of the partners the activity of the channels will grow further.

Posts will be designed to encourage people to like or follow the NINFA pages and to increase the awareness and interest on the development of the project.

Visual content, such as images and videos, can be more engaging and memorable than text-based content and can help tell the story of the NINFA project. Followers will be encouraged to share their own content related to the NINFA project in their websites and personal channels. This can include photos, videos, or testimonials.

To identify which aspects of the strategy are effective and reaching out to the audience, it is necessary to monitor and measure: a) for **website analytics**, google analytics will be used to track the number of visitors to the website, their location, how long they spend on the website, and what pages they visit. b) for **social media analytics**, the analytics tools provided by each platform will be used to track engagement metrics, for instance likes, shares, and comments. If the effectiveness is not satisfactory then different approaches will be considered.

NINFA will use four different social media platforms to target different stakeholder groups: LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Profiles have been created and are presented below in Figure 5 with a link to the specific web address. The analytics are up to 30 April 2023.

Figure 6 - Social media profiles

All partners are encouraged to follow and share the above NINFA social media accounts in order to promote the project, broaden the NINFA community and ultimately reach the 1500 followers per account as promised in the proposal. CETRI is responsible for ensuring the profiles remain up to date and active with news and relevant posts during and after the project lifetime.

The social media platforms are linked to the NINFA website and vice versa. One of the benefits of social media is that it allows people to connect and communicate with others from all over the world, to participate in discussions on a wide range of topics and also learn and grow from the diverse perspectives and viewpoints of each other. The use of hashtags helps in this sense and several are incorporated into NINFA's posts such as #groundwater, #watercycle, #hydrology, #groundwater,

#groundwatermanagement, #horizoneurope, #labsetup, #prevention, #nitrates, #fertilizers, #micropollutants.

It is important to note that the use of the '@' symbol will always be included when referring to the NINFA project on all four social media profiles!

6.6 Communication action in the future

As the project continues to advance, more communication materials will be developed to portray the research done, the new findings and any related news. Such as:

- **A poster** will soon be developed to be used in workshops or any other event the partners will attend. It can be adapted in line with the needs of specific events.
- **Videos and podcasts** with project information and interviews will be produced and uploaded in YouTube.
- **Press releases** will help to generate media coverage, which can increase the project's visibility and credibility. There will be a press release at least once a year after the annual meetings written and distributed in each partner's country.
- **Extra promotional material** will be produced as required due to clustering activities with sister projects (i.e., leaflet, poster)
- **e-Newsletter** will be published every six months summarising all activities related to the project and targeting the research and academic community, farming industry, policymakers. CETRI in collaboration with the consortium, will gather the content for the newsletter and will also oversee its distribution. All partners are encouraged to contribute articles on latest research and news items to be included in the newsletter. Each issue of the newsletter will be made available on the website and various social media platforms to increase its reach. A subscription to the newsletter will also be possible through the NINFA website. Additionally, partners and stakeholders will be prompted to share the newsletter through their own dissemination channels within their network.

All communication tools with their respective KPIs are described below in Table 4.

Table 4 NINFA Communication tools

Communication tools	Target groups	Performance indicators		Means of Verification
		P1	P2	
NINFA website with basic project info, objectives, news, open access articles and publishable deliverables	GP, SC, RP	60,000 website visits; 250 downloads per public deliverable	80,000 new visits; 300 new downloads	Website analytics
e-Newsletter summarising all activities related to the project	WI, FI, SC, G	Every 6 months, 600 recipients	Every 6 months, 600 new recipients	Newsletter subscribers
Promotional material in digital and hardcopy form (posters, leaflets/flyers)	WI, PM G, I, FI	e-material sent to 1000 recipients	2000 recipients	Project Reporting
Videos/Podcasts with project information and interviews	GP, M, G, WI	>10,000 YouTube views 10 videos / >1000 unique listeners 5 podcasts	>10,000 new YouTube views / 2,000 new listeners	Website analytics
Social media presence with project accounts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram (>5 posts per month)	GP, M, A, PM, WI	1,500 followers per project account	1,500 new followers per project account	SA
Social game mobile app enabling citizens to inform the NINFA Platform on events that may be relevant to GW management, while fostering their behavioral change	GP, M, A, PM, WI	400 citizens informing the NINFA Platform	10,000 citizens informing the NINFA Platform	Project Reporting
Project workshops: 6 thematic workshops will be organised: 1 on case studies, 1 for citizens engagement, 2 on IT tools, 2 on tech development.	G, PM, WI, GP, SC, I	>200 attendees	Established relationship with 80% of attendees	Project Reporting
Visits to schools: Each partner will visit at least one school in its territory	GP, M	>16 schools	>80 schools	Project Reporting
Presence at trade shows and events: Each partner will attend at least three events	WI, FI, I	>30 events	>50 events	Project Reporting

7 Exploitation Plan

The exploitation strategy of NINFA relates to the way each project partner individually, and the whole partnership, intend to use the project results for scientific, societal, economic purposes, as well as for policymaking. The strong industrial involvement in NINFA brings solid expertise and benefits for an effective exploitation strategy. In this framework, the NINFA consortium has defined a preliminary list of key exploitable results, specifying the ownership and their exploitation approach (Table 5).

As described in the Grant Agreement, after having defined the ownership of each result, partners will explore and define their exploitation plan e.g., patenting, knowledge exploitation, royalties, and market product development. In this way, each exploitable result will be associated with a working group for identifying specific opportunities.

The goal of NINFA is to establish a supportive system that facilitates the widespread adoption of project outcomes within the water industry, both during and after the project's completion. To accomplish this, the project will address critical factors for successful implementation, including providing assistance to partners with regards to intellectual property rights (IPR), evaluating relevant regulations and standards in Europe that impact the NINFA solutions, and creating exploitation strategies for the project's exploitable results.

Table 5 Key exploitable results, IP protection and potential market

Key Exploitable Results	Owner	IP management	Targeted sector
Train of technologies for metals recovery and pollutants removal from urban runoff	LEITAT	Internal know-how, Tech Transfer	WI, FI, RP
Train of tech. minimising nutrients and pesticides leaching in agriculture			
AOP integration for water reuse in WWTP			
Combined distributed water flow & water quality sensor	WETSUS	Patenting	WI, RP
Methodology and database for HyGenTox Chip bioassay	WETSUS	Internal know-how	WI, FI, RP
Innovative citizen engagement strategy and methodology	IMT	Copyright	WI, PM, G
Train of technologies for water reuse from urban WWTP effluents		Internal know-how, Tech Transfer	WI, RP
Social gaming design for the application	WINGS/ IMT	Copyright	GP, PM, G, I, WI
Prototype of AI GW quality model	DEL	Copyright	WI, G, RP
Denitrifying woodchip bioreactors or bioreactors with reactive layers	AQUALIA	Patenting	WI, FI, G, I
Analytical methods for contaminants quantification in GW	AQUALIA	Internal know-how	WI, G, PM, RP
NINFA Platform	WINGS	Copyright	WI, G, PM, I
Hydrogeological and reactive-transport simulation models for GW	ROMA	Internal know-how	WI, G, RP

During the project life the consortium will revise, refine, and update the preliminary list in Table 5, and a final version will be delivered at the end of the project (D6.5 M42), when partners have adjusted their initial inputs as a result of the technical development.

8 Conclusions

The deliverable D6.2 - Plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication, is a strategic document that defines the planning and scheduling of the different activities to be implemented in the frame of dissemination and communication. The aim of this deliverable is to setup an initial plan at an early stage of the project in order to coordinate in an efficient way the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities that have been agreed in the Grant Agreement of NINFA.

NINFA partners will be accountable for communicating project outcomes via NINFA social media platforms and their individual networks, while LEITAT and CETRI will oversee the utilization of online tools and channels to ensure broad exposure at the highest level.

Annex 1

NINFA Home Page

Partners

Project Framework

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe 2022 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101081865.

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Annex 2

1. NINFA D&C reporting file

The form below has been designed to help you keep track of any kind of awareness and dissemination/communication activities. Just to remind you, dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, meetings, workshops, interviews, press releases, publications, e-mails, presentations, informal discussions, seminars, etc. Please, complete any relevant parts of the form below each time you perform a dissemination or communication activity either this is small or large.

Important: Specify the type of activity as well as the type of the audience(s) addressed using the categories provided in the drop-down menu.

No. of Action	Partner (S)	Other partners involved	Basic Info			Activity details		NINFA related		Audience of the event /activity			Material used		
			Date of activity	Place of activity (City, Country or online)	Authors/Contributors	Type of activity (Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)	Title of event, conference, workshop, publications, website article, etc.	Is the activity part of NINFA?	Role and description of your organization's involvement (e.g. organizer, facilitator, interviewer, speaker, discussant, author, participant, etc.)	Type of Audience (add more lines if 2 or more apply for one entry)	Overall No of participants	Gender of Audience (if possible to estimate)	Countries addressed	Type of NinfA material used (no. of copies distributed per type of project material)	Quantity of project material used (no. of copies distributed per type of project material)
1	Los Alcazares	Aqualia	20/10/2023	Los Alcazares (Spain)		Press release	Yes	Organiser	General Public	15		Spain	leaflet	15	LINK
1	Los Alcazares	Aqualia	28/9/2023	Los Alcazares (Spain)		Press release	Yes	Organiser	General Public	15		Spain	poster	1	LINK
1	Los Alcazares	Aqualia	28/9/2023	Los Alcazares (Spain)		Press release	Yes	Organiser	General Public	15		Spain	presentation	1	LINK
2	Leitat		21/4/2023	Terrasa (Spain)	Ainhoa Gaudes	Participation in a Workshop	Yes	Speaker	Scientific Community	20		Europe	presentation	1	

2. Kick-off Meeting of ZeroPollution4water cluster

ZeroPollution4Water
Cluster

Kick-Off Meeting

 09 March 2023

 Online

THE ZEROPOLLUTION4WATER CLUSTER

KICK-OFF MEETING

09th March 2023 [online](#)

10:00 12:00 CET

Boost synergies between the twin topics

*HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-01 & HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-04
in contributing to clean water and zero pollution demonstrations in a climate change context*

3. NINFA LinkedIn profile

Funded by
the European Union

4. NINFA Facebook profile

5. NINFA Twitter profile

6. NINFA Instagram profile

<https://ninfa-project.eu/>

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the European Union